

"Advances in Organ-on-Chip Technology: Exploring Structures and Insights into Gut-on-a-Chip Models"

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Abstract :

The pharmaceutical sector has been looking for effective ways to identify new drugs with great urgency. Organ-on-a-Chip, a state-of-the-art technology, has the potential to completely transform the drug discovery process since it can simulate the physiological environment and functions of human organs on a chip for drug testing and disease modeling. It is still to be seen whether this innovative engineering platform can be successfully implemented into standard pharmaceutical and medical settings. We address the potential crucial functions that the Organ-on-a-Chip technology can play in various preclinical stages of drug discovery in this study, as well as the present obstacles to its translation and commercialization for pharmacological and medical end-users. In this review we would like to address the importance of organ chip technology, its structure, and a brief review on gut organ on chip.

Keywords: Organ-on-a-Chip, Induced pluripotent stem cells, 3D cell culture, intestine chip model,.

Introduction:

The scientific study of the organ systems and functioning of the human body is known as human physiology. This is highly relevant to the domains of toxicology, drug development, and medicine since it advances our knowledge of the pathophysiology and malfunction of the body [1]. In vivo tests on humans or model organisms are the most pertinent and straightforward ways to research human physiology. The interaction and adaptability of numerous lower-level components, including tissues, cells, proteins, and genes, are necessary for bodily activities. Therefore, using in vivo investigations alone to uncover the fundamental processes of physiological events is difficult [2]. Furthermore, the evaluation of hundreds of chemicals' physiological effects is necessary for toxicology and medication development [3].

Biologists use in vitro cell culture because low-throughput in vivo testing has certain limits. The term "cell culture" describes the expansion and upkeep of cells in a regulated setting [4]. Conventional two-dimensional (2D) cell culture methods served as a crucial platform for life science research for many years. The roles of different cells are investigated by the culture of cells or cell products using 2D systems. However, 2D systems frequently need to be verified in in vivo animal models due to their inability to adequately represent the physiological manifestations of living tissues/organs, intra-organ interactions, and microenvironmental factors [5,6]. Animal research frequently do not mimic human tests due to species differences [7], and the use of animals as drug test models has come under fire due to ethical concerns and costly expenses.

Inadequate depiction of the human tissue milieu in preclinical experiments can result in imprecise forecasts of the aggregate impacts of whole tissue functionality [8]. OOAC was created to address these drawbacks by offering a greater number of physiological model systems [9]. It was suggested that OOAC will eventually replace animal models used in experiments [10].

Figure 1. Microfluidic Organ-on-a-Chip platform. Preclinical studies rely on major tools (i.e., 2D or 3D in vitro cell cultures, and in vivo animal models) for drug development. 2D in vitro cultures offer a rapid and reproducible way to analyze drug responses; however, they lack the 3D physiological tissue environment. Conventional 3D cell cultures in a hydrogel matrix can provide a 3D culture environment, but still fall short to controllably recapitulate the in vivo physiology and pathology of the human body. Animal models enable in vivo analysis, yet the species differences between animal and human physiological mechanisms and complexity of the in vivo physiology weaken the accuracy and reproducibility of experimental results. Microfluidic Organ-on-Chip platforms that enable controllable cell culture within an organotypic microarchitectural environment provide a simple, yet more physiologically relevant, platform to controllably and systematically interrogate human biology. Figure generated using BioRender (BioRender.com).

Basic elements of organ on chip

Cell sourcing remains a significant challenge in the field of Organ-on-Chip (OoC) research. Currently, researchers populate platforms with primary tissues from donors, commercially available immortalized cell lines, or induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) sourced either commercially or from donors. While primary tissues are ideal for seeding OoCs, especially for rare diseases, they are often limited in availability, particularly from small or diseased populations. Cell lines or mixed primary cells introduce increased genetic variability, potentially complicating results.¹¹

Induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) emerge as a promising source for OoC platforms. Advances in technology allow the generation of renewable cell sources from various tissues. Reprogramming blood cells or skin fibroblasts into iPSCs offers advantages such as isogenic backgrounds and the ability to study monogenic diseases through gene editing techniques.¹² Recent studies demonstrate the potential of iPSCs in verifying population-wide studies, such as in the Framingham heart study cohort.¹³

The biomechanical environment significantly influences stem cell phenotype,⁹ with 3D cultures often yielding higher yields and more mature phenotypes.^{14 15 16} Microfluidic environments in tissue chips enable precise control over cell differentiation, promising advancements in the iPSC field and providing renewable cell sources for OoC research.

Differentiation protocols for iPSC-derived cells vary, often resembling fetal phenotypes. Standardizing protocols may take time, given the young nature of the field. Epigenetic memory and patient-derived iPSCs offer valuable tools for cancer research and drug development.^{17, 18}

Establishing a **universal cell culture medium or "blood surrogate"** ¹⁹for linked OoC tissue systems poses a challenge. Approaches involve recirculating systems or modifying individual modules to mimic blood flow.

The extracellular matrix (ECM) plays a crucial role in tissue organization and cell signaling. Utilizing decellularized scaffolds or synthetic hydrogels requires careful consideration of 3D arrangement and ECM composition to support tissue characteristics.^{20 21 22}

Scaling organs in OoC platforms presents challenges in maintaining physiological relevance between different systems. Functional scaling, considering tissue function, offers a potential solution to ensure proper organ-specific functions in OoC platforms.^{23 24}

Models of Microfluidic Intestine Chips

Microfluidic Intestine Chip Models offer a sophisticated approach to simulate intestinal functions. These devices, with microchannels less than 1 mm wide, facilitate controlled fluid flow at nano litre to microlitre scales, suitable for cell culture. By perfusing culture medium through microchannels, they replicate dynamic fluid flows and shear stresses akin to those in the human intestinal lumen and blood capillaries. This precise control allows for regulated delivery of nutrients, drugs, or toxins to intestinal epithelium cultured on the microfluidic channels. 25, 26

Most Intestine Chips feature two hollow channels separated by a porous membrane coated with extracellular matrix (ECM), housing immortalized human intestinal epithelial cells. 27 This setup enables the study of tight junction barrier function, nutrient absorption, and drug interactions. Some models integrate multiple chambers with different cell types for pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic assessments. However, limitations such as low cell density and short culture duration have been observed.

To better mimic the 3D structure of the human intestine, micro molding techniques have been employed to create polymeric scaffolds resembling villi. Culturing intestinal epithelial cells on these structures promotes morphological and functional similarities to the native intestine. However, barrier function analysis is hindered due to the solid polymer material blocking access to the epithelium's abluminal surface. 28,29

A multichannel Intestine Chip known as HuMiX employs nanoporous membranes to separate luminal microbial compartments from layers of intestinal epithelium.³⁰ This model supports co-culture of Caco-2 cells and anaerobic gut bacteria with continuous perfusion, though without mimicking mechanical deformations like peristalsis. Additionally, its short survival time limits long-term studies of host-microbial interactions and intestinal pathophysiology.

A mechanically active Gut Chip model has been developed to address these shortcomings. It allows the growth, coexistence, and interaction of human intestinal epithelium, capillary endothelium, immune cells, and commensal microbial cells under physiologically relevant fluid flow and peristalsis-like mechanical deformations. This chip, made of flexible, gas-permeable silicone polymer, facilitates high-resolution imaging and continuous fluid flow, enabling long-term coculture without compromising barrier integrity or cellular function.

The Gut Chip's ability to simulate the dynamic human intestinal microenvironment more faithfully offers new insights into intestinal function and disease mechanisms, such as chronic inflammatory diseases like inflammatory bowel disease (IBD).³¹ By integrating pathogenic bacteria and commensal microbes, it provides a platform to study complex immune-microbiome interactions relevant to intestinal homeostasis and disease development.

Fig 2 : Concept of “gut-axis” organ-on-a-chip (I) Conventional in vitro models and animal models are physiologically different from the human body. They also hinder the understanding of human diseases and the development of new therapeutic strategies [32] ©Copyright 2021, MDPI. (II) The concept of the GoC simulates the dynamic 3D microenvironment of an organ on a small scale. (a) Human-gut-microbiome on a chip [33] ©Copyright 2019, Nature.; (b) Establishment of long-term homeostatic culture of tubular mini-guts [34]©Copyright 2020, Nature. (III) “Gut-axis” organ-on-a-chip. (c) Gut–brain axis on chip [5] ©Copyright 2021, Elsevier. (d) Gut–lung axis on chip [36] (e) Gut–kidney axis on chip [37] ©Copyright 2021, Elsevier. (f) Gut–liver axis on chip [38] ©Copyright 2017, Wiley [39] ©Copyright 2021, Nature. [40] ©Copyright 2020, Royal Soc Chemistry.

Conclusion :

Researchers can use a synthetic biology approach at the cell, tissue, and organ levels with the help of microfluidic Organ Chip systems, which offer unmatched independent control over multiple key biologic, chemical, molecular, cellular, and mechanical parameters within the intestinal microenvironment. This can result in new insights into intestinal physiology and disease mechanisms. By utilizing these special qualities, Intestine Chips can be used to investigate the molecular mechanisms behind different enteropathies and to progress the creation of novel treatments. Precision medicine will advance with the development of customized intestinal chips that contain stem cells, immune cells, and microbiome from the same patient. These chips will provide a potent new method for defining patient-specific drug responses and toxicities. Since this subject is still developing, there is still more to be done to strengthen these models' robustness and confirm their applicability to the creation of drugs and personalized medicine. But it's becoming more and more obvious what benefits they offer over traditional cultural systems and even enteroid civilizations.

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